

ESM H

Confidence Intervals and Prediction Intervals of the Pooled Intercorrelations

Variable	H	E	X	A	C	O	D
H	(.76, .80) [.64, .86]	(.01, .07) [-.14, .22]	(-.03, .04) [-.21, .22]	(.35, .41) [.22, .51]	(.25, .32) [.08, .47]	(.08, .14) [-.05, .27]	(-.31, -.24) [-.45, -.08]
E	(.01, .05) [-.08, .14]	(.74, .78) [.62, .85]	(-.22, -.08) [-.54, .29]	(-.12, -.04) [-.31, .16]	(.00, .06) [-.14, .19]	(-.04, .05) [-.24, .25]	(.13, .20) [-.05, .36]
X	(-.02, .03) [-.13, .14]	(-.17, -.06) [-.44, .24]	(.80, .84) [.62, .92]	(.00, .11) [-.27, .37]	(.24, .31) [.05, .47]	(.11, .19) [-.10, .39]	(-.40, -.33) [-.55, -.15]
A	(.27, .31) [.23, .35]	(-.010, -.04) [-.22, .09]	(.01, .09) [-.20, .29]	(.76, .80) [.61, .87]	(.06, .13) [-.10, .29]	(.10, .15) [-.01, .26]	(-.21, -.15) [-.32, -.03]
C	(.20, .25) [.11, .33]	(.00, .04) [-.07, .11]	(.19, .24) [.07, .35]	(.05, .10) [-.05, .20]	(.78, .81) [.68, .87]	(.20, .28) [-.02, .47]	(-.41, -.33) [-.55, -.15]
O	(.06, .11) [-.02, .19]	(-.03, .03) [-.15, .14]	(.09, .15) [-.04, .28]	(.07, .12) [.00, .19]	(.16, .21) [.04, .32]	(.77, .80) [.68, .86]	(-.06, .03) [-.28, .25]
D	(-.26, -.21) [-.36, -.09]	(.010, .16) [-.01, .27]	(-.34, -.27) [-.47, -.12]	(-.17, -.13) [-.24, -.07]	(-.34, -.28) [-.47, -.13]	(-.04, .03) [-.21, .19]	(.89, .92) [.72, .97]

Note. The lower off diagonal depicts the 95% Confidence intervals in (x) and the 95% Prediction intervals in [x] of the pooled raw correlation coefficients from Table 2. The upper off diagonal shows the same intervals for the pooled corrected correlation coefficients. The diagonal contains the same intervals for the pooled average reliability of the scales.